

The Creation of New Businesses at a Global Level

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The variable "New businesses per thousand inhabitants aged 15-64" represents an economic indicator that measures the number of new entrepreneurial ventures started within a given period in relation to the active population aged between 15 and 64. This age group is considered the most relevant for economic and productive development, as it includes the majority of individuals actively participating in the labor market and who are of the right age to embark on new entrepreneurial initiatives. Measuring this per thousand inhabitants standardizes the data, making it comparable between countries or regions with different population sizes, providing a more accurate picture of the entrepreneurial dynamism of a given area. This variable is particularly important for assessing the economic vitality of a country or region, as a high number of new businesses is generally associated with an environment conducive to innovation, supportive entrepreneurship policies, and a growing economy. Conversely, a low value might indicate difficulties in accessing credit, restrictive regulations, or unfavorable economic conditions that discourage the creation of new ventures. Additionally, the number of new businesses may be influenced by cultural, educational, and infrastructural factors that either facilitate or hinder entrepreneurship. Monitoring this variable allows for a better understanding of the degree of resilience and adaptability of an economy, as new businesses contribute to renewing the economic fabric and creating new job opportunities. Finally, this indicator can be used for international or regional comparisons, helping to identify successful models in the implementation of policies that foster business development and highlight areas where improvements are needed. The data refers to the period 2013-2022.

New Businesses per Thousand Inhabitants Aged 15-64 in 2022. The data on "New businesses per thousand inhabitants aged 15-64" in 2022 shows significant variation between countries, highlighting notable disparities in global entrepreneurial activity. At the top of the ranking is Estonia, with an extraordinary rate of 100 new businesses per thousand inhabitants. This figure can be attributed to several factors, including government policies strongly focused on supporting innovation, favorable regulations for startups, and access to affordable financing. Estonia is often regarded as a success story for digitalization and technological development, and these figures confirm its position as a leader in the entrepreneurial landscape. Hong Kong, with 79.4 new businesses per thousand inhabitants, and the United Kingdom, with 74.8, reaffirm their status as major global business hubs, thanks to robust financial ecosystems, favorable regulations, and international markets. Countries like Botswana (74.3) and New Zealand (73.9) also rank among the top, demonstrating that a favorable entrepreneurial environment can exist even in smaller economies far from traditional economic centers. Botswana, in particular, showcases how an emerging economy can thrive through policies that incentivize the private sector and small business markets. Luxembourg and Cyprus, with 71 and 54.8 new businesses per thousand inhabitants, respectively, reflect the importance of favorable tax policies and a stable economic environment for the creation of new businesses, even in smaller countries. Australia (58.9) and South Africa (51.6) also show significant rates, thanks to policies promoting entrepreneurship and the availability of venture capital, particularly in the tech sector. Iceland, with 43 new businesses per thousand inhabitants, continues to demonstrate a dynamic entrepreneurial ecosystem, despite its small population. This success is likely the result of national policies aimed at supporting innovation and creativity. Similarly, Sweden and Norway, with 37 and 38.9 new businesses, respectively, reflect their tradition of supporting new entrepreneurial ventures,

particularly in the tech and startup sectors. Further down the ranking, countries like Italy and Lithuania (both at 12.1) show relatively low rates of new business creation compared to leading countries. In Italy, labor market rigidity, complex bureaucracy, and limited access to financing may explain this situation. However, economic stability and support for key sectors like tourism and agri-food continue to generate new entrepreneurial opportunities. At the bottom of the ranking are countries like Pakistan (0.4), Iraq (0.2), and Niger (0.2), which show extremely low rates of new businesses. Economic difficulties, political instability, and lack of adequate infrastructure are some of the factors holding back entrepreneurial activity in these nations. These figures indicate the need to improve economic and legislative conditions to foster business development. A surprising figure comes from Japan (1.7), a highly developed economy with a very low rate of new businesses. This can be attributed to the country's demographic structure, characterized by a high percentage of elderly population, and a more conservative entrepreneurial culture that tends to favor large, established companies over new initiatives. Similarly, Germany (5.5) and Canada (0.7) present lower rates than expected for economically advanced countries, indicating that, despite strong economies, barriers to entry for new businesses can still be significant. In conclusion, the data reveals a strong diversity in the rate of new businesses globally, reflecting the economic, political, and cultural conditions of each country. Nations with favorable policies, easy access to capital, and support for innovation tend to be the top performers, while those facing more structural challenges struggle to generate new entrepreneurial ventures.

New Businesses per Thousand Inhabitants Aged 15-64 Between 2013 and 2022. The data on new businesses per thousand inhabitants aged between 15 and 64 from 2013 to 2022 provides a varied overview of the evolution of entrepreneurship across different countries. One key aspect is the significant gap between the "top performers," who experienced substantial growth, and the "worse performers," who saw dramatic declines, reflecting the diverse economic, political, and cultural conditions that have influenced the entrepreneurial landscape. Panama stands out as the country with the most impressive growth, jumping from 0.5 to 17.3 new businesses per thousand inhabitants, with an astonishing percentage increase of 3360%. This figure is surprising and could be explained by economic reforms, incentives for new business ventures, or robust economic recovery. South Africa also recorded a significant increase (+873.58%), signaling a dynamic entrepreneurial environment despite the country's socioeconomic challenges. Another notable country is Ethiopia, which saw an 850% increase, transforming itself into an emerging player, demonstrating that even less developed economies can foster a favorable environment for entrepreneurship. Among other top performers, Uzbekistan (+98.21%), Tunisia (+88.37%), Poland (+83.33%), and Estonia (+79.21%) show how a combination of favorable policies, economic growth, and targeted investments can significantly boost the creation of new businesses. Estonia, in particular, has seen remarkable growth, likely due to its advanced digital ecosystem and strong government support for technological innovation. However, many countries have experienced sharp declines. Among the worst performers is Canada, which saw a dramatic drop of 98.65%, falling from 52 to 0.7 new businesses per thousand inhabitants. This could reflect challenges related to the pandemic, reduced public support, or market saturation. Bulgaria also experienced a significant decline (-88.5%), suggesting a deep crisis in the entrepreneurial sector, possibly linked to economic or demographic factors. Other countries, such as Costa Rica (-85.2%), Israel (-59.28%), and Latvia (-63.19%), show negative trends that could be associated with a variety of causes, including economic instability, changes in government policies, and international competition. Overall, the decline seen in many countries, including Germany (-40.86%), Spain (-42.69%), and Italy (-8.03%), could result from a combination of factors: international competition, digitalization that favors the concentration of economic activities in large tech companies, and reduced barriers to entry for already established businesses. This phenomenon may have led to a

decrease in small and medium-sized enterprises, which have traditionally accounted for a significant portion of new entrepreneurial ventures. On the other hand, emerging economies like Ethiopia and Togo appear to have found growth opportunities in an economic development context, showing how entrepreneurship promotion policies, even in less developed economies, can yield remarkable results. In conclusion, the data reveals strong heterogeneity in countries' ability to promote the creation of new businesses. While some countries have seen significant expansion, others are experiencing a worrying decline, often linked to adverse economic conditions or global competition. These findings highlight the importance of targeted policies and a stable economic environment to promote entrepreneurial growth.

Conclusions. The number of new businesses decreased between 2013 and 2022, dropping from an average of 22.11 to 17.54 for the countries considered, representing a decline of -20.64%. The top-performing countries are: Panama with +3360.00%; South Africa with +873.58%; Ethiopia with +850.00%; Togo with +362.50%; and Pakistan with +100.00%. The worst-performing countries are: Argentina with -77.42%; Japan with -77.63%; Costa Rica with -85.20%; Bulgaria with -88.51%; and Canada with -98.65%.

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Panama	0,5	17,3	16,8	3360,00
	South Africa	5,3	51,6	46,3	873,58
	Ethiopia	0,2	1,9	1,7	850,00
	Togo	0,8	3,7	2,9	362,50
	Pakistan	0,2	0,4	0,2	100,00
Worse Performers	Argentina	3,1	0,7	-2,4	-77,42
	Japan	7,6	1,7	-5,9	-77,63
	Costa Rica	100	14,8	-85,2	-85,20
	Bulgaria	49,6	5,7	-43,9	-88,51
	Canada	52	0,7	-51,3	-98,65

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